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Editorial

REPRESENT: A New Beginning

Editors

REPRESENT: Research on Practices around Religion, Ethnicity and Society is a new biannual (spring and autumn), peer-reviewed, cross-disciplinary and interdisciplinary English-language journal that covers a broad range of themes across the humanities and social sciences.

The Journal is double-blind peer-reviewed and open-access, although we do not currently charge any article processing fees. However, we will not publish any article without rigorous peer review and will not respond to or entertain any inquiries regarding expedited processing and publication.

REPRESENT is published by SABAR Institute, Kolkata, registered as a trust under the Trust Act of West Bengal, that focuses on addressing social disparities, fostering social cohesion, and promoting social justice through evidence-based research aimed at creating an inclusive India and the world. Besides, SABAR Institute also runs an inter-faith initiative, Know Your Neighbour, in Kolkata and beyond. Visit the website of the SABAR Institute to know more about our work.

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The inaugural issue of the journal, *REPRESENT: Research on Practices around Religion, Ethnicity and Society*, is finally seeing the light of the day after months of hard works by all the contributors and the editorial team. There is no dearth of journals in the market, for those looking for quality papers and commentaries, there are ample reputed publications but those usually take years to publish. For those looking for quick publications there are many local journals as well sham academic and predatory journals who have turned the *publish or perish* system into an exploitative business.

At *REPRESENT*, however, we hope to evolve into a new academic space in public discourse by making critical interventions, offering fresh insights, countering and reframing established narratives, and setting a new agenda vis-à-vis race and ethnicity. We seek to promote critical study of the complex interplay among media and fields such as social, political, cultural, spatial, intellectual, and more.

The title *REPRESENT* indicates the focus of the journal as a critical academic space for publishing *Research on Practices around Religion, Ethnicity, and Society*, encompassing divergent issues of ethnic and cultural-religious minorities, and gender, including their representations in media, films, and popular culture, as well as in social, political, and educational institutions. The key focus areas for the journal will be:

- Critical analysis of public policies and popular practices related to ethnicity, race, religion, and society, with a focus on adherence to constitutional morality and reform-oriented recommendations.
- Qualitative and quantitative, data-driven analyses of participation by gender, racial, and ethnic groups in social, economic, and political domains.
- Representations of gender, religion, ethnicity, and society in social, political, and educational institutions.
- Tracking and offering critical analysis of media representations of gender, race, and ethnicity in India and the world.
- Fostering counter-narratives, decolonial perspectives, and community media practices.

No article in the journal will be cleared without rigorous peer-reviewed and editorial scrutiny. However, particularly targeting young scholars, articles that will have potentials and scope of improvements will be given a fair chance of revision before being outrightly rejected.

The inaugural issue of the journal comprises five research articles and a book review. The first article in this volume, is titled, **‘Deciphering Differences: Student Interpretations of Secularism in Public Universities and Colleges in West Bengal, India,’** authored by Ishita Biswas and Biswadeep Bhattacharyya. It positions secularism as a lived and communicative practice, by tracing how students in public universities and colleges in West Bengal, India, mediate religious difference in everyday academic contexts. The findings of the study demonstrate that diversity operates differently across settings, constraining expression in classrooms while enabling it in broader institutional spaces.

The second article, titled **‘Female Objectification, Insensitivity and Performative Aggression in an Online Contemporary Comedy Show *India’s Got Latent*’** by Ariza Tabassum and Kaifia Ancer Laskar, explores the intersection of comedy and censorship in India through a content analysis of the controversial show. It examines how the show pushed boundaries by addressing taboo topics such as sexuality, politics, and social issues. The use of offensive slang, sexual innuendo, and provocative commentary may not always violate formal censorship rules, but it can challenge societal norms. This shock value becomes commercially profitable consequently rewarding the comedians who escalate vulgarity to remain relevant.

The third article, titled **‘Whose Classroom Is It? Language And Cultural Representation In Digital Learning Videos Across State, National, And Global Platforms,’** by Sohini Biswas, explores digital learning videos as sites of representation and also examines how educational media produced at different levels of platform governance shape the imagined classroom specifically in secondary education. Adopting a qualitative exploratory content analysis, this study compares ten publicly accessible secondary level instructional videos drawn from three platforms: a state-level initiative (*Banglar Shiksha Online, West Bengal*), a national level platform (*Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing or DIKSHA, India*), and a global level platform (*Khan Academy*). The study reveals a systematic representational shift as state level videos foregrounds on linguistic accessibility and easy to relate cultural familiarity, hence embedding learning within local contexts, while national level content prioritises more on standardisation and curricular uniformity, thus, neutralising regional diversity, and global platforms adopts culturally abstract and language emphasising scalability and individualised learning, hence, almost detaching knowledge from social and cultural contexts. Critically, these patterns highlight how educational media despite its

glamourised promise of inclusion may actually reproduce existing inequalities by privileging dominant epistemologies.

The fourth article, titled **‘Political Violence in Regional Cinematic Expression: A Critical Analysis of a Select Bengali Film’** by Rosona Khatun, Kaifia Ancer Laskar and Mohammad Reyaz, conducts a narrative analysis, taking a Bengali film *Dharmajuddha* (2022), as a case study, to flag the discursive use of political and ethnic violence in regional filmic text. The dominant tropes used in this film through omission, trivialization and condemnation revolve around the portrayal of people belonging to the margins who become the primary victims of political and ethnic violence.

The fifth article in the Issue, titled **‘What Makes ‘Sensational’ Sexual Crime Stories on the Front Pages? A Critical Analysis of News Values’** by Francis Philip Barclay, tries to answer the deceptively simple question of ‘what makes the popular sexual crime stories?’ By conducting content analysis of front page news articles on sexual violence that were published in three newspapers, *The Times of India* (New Delhi edition), *Hindustan Times* (New Delhi edition) and *The Telegraph* (Kolkata edition), the article measures the prevalence of and the priority accorded to popular news values, identifying their patterns.

This Issue also carries a **book review by Zeeshan Husain of the book, *Roads to Freedom: Prisoners in Colonial India*, authored by Mushirul Hasan** in 2016, former Vice Chance Chancellor of Jamia Millia Islamia and reputed history of modern India who passed away in 2018. The book highlights that prisons were unique spaces where freedom fighters across the undivided India could meet and discuss with each other. By studying their internment and the exchanges they had with each other, the book underlines a paradox: despite large-scale imprisonment, freedom movement did not slow down. Jail is theorised as a happening space where a different kind of freedom struggle was waged. The reviewer, however, points out that the book does not mention any Christian freedom fighters nor has detailed any Sikh political prisoners. Hasan is also silent on Independence movement in south India or Adivasi assertion against British India. Despite these drawbacks, the book makes it mark by humanising political prisoners and giving them voices.

For the inaugural issue, as well as overall scope of the journal, we welcome readers’ feedback and comments, and may highlight some of those on our social media. Our Autumn issue should be published by the end of the year, and we solicit articles, reviews and commentaries for our future issues. Visit our website for all necessary information, and article submission guidelines.

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3 **Francis P. Barclay** is a faculty member in the Department of Media and Communication, School of Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, India. Dr. Barclay is also an accomplished media researcher, psephologist and writer with a background in journalism, news art and political cartooning. He is the founder-editor of the Journal of Media and Communication (UGC-CARE listed). He is the co-author of Sexual Violence and Predatory Journalism in India: Emerging Unethical Practices (Routledge, 2025) and co-editor of Media and Conflict: Critical Analysis of News Discourses in India (Springer Nature, 2025), Social Media in India: Regulatory Needs, Issues and Challenges (Sage, 2022) and Gender and Popular Visual Culture in India: 'Benevolent' Sexism and Disguised Discrimination (Routledge, 2023). Dr. Barclay has also served several English newspapers in India. Some of his works are available on his personal website, www.francisbarclay.com.

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